

Determinants of PPE Accounting Method among Listed Non-Financial Firms in selected African Commonwealth Countries

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the determinants of property, plant and equipment (PPE) among listed non-financial firms in selected African Commonwealth Countries. Four hypotheses were formulated for testing in the study. The independent variables were assets tangibility, leverage, firm size and firm age while dependent variable is PPE. The study employed the *ex-post facto* research design with a population comprising of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria, South Africa and Kenya for the year ended 2013-2022. Panel regression was used to test the hypotheses and the results of the study showed that assets tangibility, firm leverage and firm age are determinant of PPE of listed non-financial firms in African Commonwealth Countries at 1%-5% level of significance. Firm size on the other hand was found not to determine PPE of listed non-financial firms. The study therefore concluded that the determinants of property, plant and equipment of listed non-financial firms in African Commonwealth Countries include; assets tangibility, firm leverage, firm age other than firm size. Based on the above findings, the study recommended amongst others that firms should focus on improving the transparency and details of their tangible asset reporting. Also, firms should maintain an optimal debt-to-equity ratio and regularly review the impact of leverage on financial reporting and PPE accounting practices.

Keyword: PPE; Assets Tangibility; Leverage; Firm Size; Firm Age

1. INTRODUCTION

Commonwealth African countries, boasting substantial market sizes and advantageous geographic locations, have become attractive investment destinations due to factors such as low labour costs and potential market expansion. However, the journey towards financial reporting harmonization in these nations is impeded by various challenges including unstable legal frameworks, state intervention in business operations, and low productivity levels (Stawicka, 2014).

Listed firms in African Commonwealth countries invest substantially in non-current assets, encompassing various items like plant and machinery, office equipment, and buildings. These assets incur significant maintenance expenses, driven by factors such as maintenance agreements, sudden breakdowns, and inefficiencies in equipment utilization. The consequential high repair costs, coupled with challenges in project management and global economic dynamics, underscore the importance of effective asset management. Choosing an appropriate accounting method for Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE) becomes imperative. As per International Accounting Standards (IAS) 16, firms can opt to report PPE at

original cost or revalue them periodically. The choice of measurement basis profoundly impacts financial reporting and decision-making for stakeholders, including investors, creditors, and employees.

Despite numerous empirical studies on PPE accounting, some research gap persists within the context of African Commonwealth countries. Past research has predominantly focused on Asian and Indian contexts, with limited attention to Africa and particularly non-financial firms (Alexandra et al, 2016). Furthermore, existing studies often confined themselves to single-country analyses and employed estimation methods that may not adequately capture heterogeneity effects (Osirim & Moses, 2019; Thankgod, 2021; Anuar et al, 2021).

Again, prior studies have typically concentrated on single-country analyses, often within stable political and economic environments (JanHoras & Denny, 2019; Anuar et al., 2021). Such studies rarely conduct comprehensive comparative analyses across different regulatory environments. Therefore, there is a need for a robust analysis that compares results from various countries under study and examines the implications for the sub-Saharan business environment.

To address these gaps, this study aimed at analyzing the determinants of PPE accounting choice among listed firms in African Commonwealth countries. By including variables such as asset tangibility, leverage, firm size, firm age and taxation and employing robust panel regression techniques, this research sought to provide clear insights into the factors driving PPE accounting decisions in this specific context. Additionally, extending the analysis over a ten-year period with a larger sample size enhanced the comprehensiveness and reliability of the findings, contributing to a deeper understanding of PPE accounting practices in the region.

To achieve this purpose, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H₀₁: Asset tangibility is not a significant predictor of PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African Commonwealth Countries.

H₀₂: Leverage does not significantly explain PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African Commonwealth Countries.

H₀₃: Firm size is not a significant predictor of PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African Commonwealth Countries.

H₀₄: Firm age does not significantly explain PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African Commonwealth Countries.

2. Review of Related Literature

2.1. Property, Plants and Equipment (PPE)

Non-current assets investment plays a vital role in carrying out operational activities and enhances the capacity of an organization in providing goods and services. These investment items include plant and machinery (office equipment, information and communication technology), buildings, motor vehicle, furniture, and fittings (Akparhuere et al, 2019; JanHoras & Denny, 2019; Osirim & Moses, 2019; Thankgod, 2021; Anuar et al, 2021). There are many reasons why non-current assets are considered as one of the most investment elements in an organization.

Okoro and Charles (2019), opined that effective investment of non-current assets is one of the most important elements of firms in creating value for shareholders. High non-current assets turnover ratio indicates efficient utilization of non-current assets in generating sales while a low ratio indicates inefficient investment and utilization of non-current assets. If non-current assets are not invested properly, then there is the likely chance that organizations will not perform as expected (Anuar et al, 2021). Successful organizations know how to invest in non-current assets for efficient accomplishment of organizational goals and adapt to changes in external environment as well as change in technology.

PPE are essentially long-term assets of a firm and usually include buildings and other real estate acquisitions, furniture, equipment, vehicles, and ICT infrastructure which may include hardware and software (Investopedia, 2013). Non-current assets may be tangible or intangible. The direct linkage between investment in non-current assets and performance, they noted that not only that non-current asset investment enhances the ability of firms to generate profit, but equally stressed its importance on the daily operations of firms. According to Magoulios (2006), the totality of the cost of economy involved in the

purchase of new plants and machinery with the aim of increasing the stocks of raw materials and products for new homes is referred to as investment on a macroeconomic level. Philippa (2005) defines investment as a commitment of certain amount of money, in the present year, whose return is increased earnings in the future. The study opines that investment in non-current assets like buildings, motor vehicles, and other equipment and so on determines the operational effectiveness of most industries. These non-current assets are normally shown on the statement of financial position and account for a large portion of a company's value.

2.1.1 PPE Accounting Method

According to Badingatus et al. (2020) revaluation of non-current assets is classifying into two method (a) non-current are owned to be used in the production or supply of goods or services to be repurchased by other parties, or for administrative purposes and b) are estimated to be used for more than one period. Accounting standards explicitly allow management to choose one method of measuring non-current assets after initial recognition, namely the cost model or revaluation model. Under the cost model, non-current assets are reported at cost less accumulated depreciation and accumulated impairment losses. Under International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS), the rules for measurement of property, plant and equipment are presented in IAS 16 Property, Plant and Equipment (2011) and, when adopting IFRS for the first time, (in IFRS 1 First-time Adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (2011). IAS 16 allows two valuation models for measurement of property, plant and equipment after its recognition: the cost model and the revaluation model.

According to paragraph 29 of IAS 16, after recognition of an item of property, plant and equipment as an asset, an entity shall choose either the cost model or the revaluation model as its accounting policy and shall apply that policy to an entire class of property, plant, and equipment. Under the cost model, property, plant, and equipment are carried at its historical cost less any accumulated depreciation and any impairments (IAS 16, 30). Under the revaluation model, after recognition as an asset, property, plant, and equipment whose fair value can be measured reliably are carried at a revalued amount, being its fair value at the date of the revaluation less any later accumulated depreciation and later accumulated impairment losses (IAS 16, 31). Revaluations are to be made so that the carrying amount does not differ significantly from fair value.

2.1.1.1 Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE) Accounting Methods Before IFRS

Before the adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), Nigerian companies primarily used the historical cost method for valuing PPE. This approach involved recording assets at their original purchase price and subsequently subtracting accumulated depreciation. The Nigerian Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (NGAAP) governed these practices. NGAAP provided basic guidelines for accounting for PPE, but it lacked comprehensive standards on asset revaluation. As a result, there were inconsistencies on how different firms reported and disclosed their PPE values. The lack of detailed revaluation guidance often led to undervalued asset bases, affecting the accuracy of financial statements and making it difficult for investors to assess the true value of companies' assets.

In Kenya, before the implementation of IFRS, companies also relied on historical cost accounting for their PPE. Assets were recorded at their initial cost minus any accumulated depreciation and impairment losses over time. The local Kenyan GAAP governed these practices, which, like NGAAP, provided basic but not comprehensive guidelines for PPE accounting. This often resulted in significant variations on how companies valued and reported their PPE. The lack of detailed standards on revaluation and impairment testing under Kenyan GAAP meant that asset values could become outdated, thereby reducing the relevance and reliability of financial statements for decision-making purposes.

Before adopting IFRS, South African companies followed the historical cost convention for accounting for PPE. This method involved recording assets at their purchase price and then deducting accumulated depreciation over their useful lives. South African GAAP, which governed these practices, was relatively more developed compared to the standards in other African countries. However, despite being more advanced, South African GAAP still lacked the comprehensiveness and detail provided by IFRS, particularly in areas such as asset revaluation and impairment testing. This sometimes led to inconsistencies and a lack of comparability in financial statements.

2.1.1.2 Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE) Accounting Methods After IFRS

Nigeria officially adopted IFRS in 2012, marking a significant shift in its accounting landscape. Under IFRS, particularly IAS 16, companies are required to provide more detailed and standardized information about their PPE. One of the major changes introduced by IFRS was the option to use the revaluation model, in addition to the traditional cost model. The revaluation model allows companies to measure PPE at fair value, which can provide a more accurate reflection of the current value of these assets. This has led to a higher degree of transparency and comparability in financial reporting. Moreover, IFRS mandates extensive disclosures about PPE, including information on depreciation methods, useful lives of assets, carrying amounts of each class of PPE, and revaluation surpluses. These disclosures have enhanced the quality and reliability of financial statements, providing stakeholders with better insights into a company's asset management and valuation practices.

Kenya began the process of adopting IFRS in 1999, with full adoption completed by 2005. IFRS standards, particularly IAS 16, introduced more rigorous and standardized requirements for accounting for PPE. Under IFRS, Kenyan firms can choose between the cost model and the revaluation model. The revaluation model, which allows PPE to be carried at fair value, has become increasingly popular as it provides a more accurate and up-to-date valuation of assets. This shift has led to greater consistency and comparability in financial reporting. Furthermore, IFRS requires comprehensive disclosures about PPE, including the methods of depreciation used, the useful lives of assets, and details about revaluation surpluses and impairment losses. These detailed disclosures have significantly improved the transparency and reliability of financial statements, making them more useful for investors, analysts, and other stakeholders (Omondi & Muturi, 2013).

South Africa adopted IFRS in 2005, which brought significant changes to its accounting practices for PPE. With the adoption of IFRS, particularly IAS 16, companies in South Africa were given the option to use either the historical cost model or the revaluation model for PPE. The revaluation model allows for assets to be measured at fair value, which provides a more realistic and current valuation. This transition to IFRS has improved the quality of financial reporting by making it more transparent and comparable. Additionally, IFRS requires detailed disclosures about PPE, including the basis of measurement, the depreciation methods used, the useful lives of assets, and the details of any impairment losses and revaluation surpluses. These extensive disclosures help ensure that financial statements provide a clear and accurate picture of a company's financial position, thereby enhancing the decision-making process for investors and other stakeholders.

2.1.2 Determinants of PPE Accounting Method

For the purpose of this study, the determinants of the propensity to revalue PPE covered in this study includes; the asset tangibility, leverage, firm size, firm age, and taxation of the firms.

2.1.2.1 Asset Tangibility

Tangibility is defined as the fixed asset to total asset ratio. Fixed assets are significant in determining a firm's leverage level. A company with a high number of fixed assets can borrow at a reduced interest rate by pledging the security of these assets to creditors. With the incentive of obtaining debt at a lower interest rate, a business with a larger percentage of fixed assets is expected to borrow more than a firm with a higher cost of borrowing due to having less fixed assets. Tangible assets are less susceptible to informational asymmetries and have a higher value in the case of bankruptcy than intangible assets. According to the tradeoff theory, there is a positive link between leverage measurements and the share of tangible assets. According to this idea, Bradley et al. (1984) as cited in (Chen, Shan, Wang, Yang & Zhang, 2024) discovered that leverage is positively connected to the degree of tangibility. Tangibility of assets was quantified by Rajan and Zingales (1995), Odinga (2003), and Kuria (2010) as the ratio of total fixed assets to total assets.

In this study, tangibility will be defined as fixed/tangible assets divided by total assets. The Conceptual Framework for Financial Reporting (2018) defines assets as “resources controlled by the entity (i.e., firm, as a type of entity) as a result of past events and from which future economic benefits are expected to flow to the entity”. For accounting purposes, they are categorized as short-term versus long-term assets, and tangible versus intangible assets. Musah, Kong and Osei (2019) described tangible assets as physical

items of value that are not subject to sale for its customers and are used to generate income. Tangible assets can be classified into two types: (i) current assets -such as cash and cash equivalents, marketable securities, accounts receivable and inventory- with a lifespan of up to one year (short-term) that can easily be converted into cash without loss in value in times of emergency; and (ii) fixed assets -such as property, plant and equipment- for long-term (more than one accounting period) use with relatively low market liquidity. Apart from tangible assets, a firm may have some other long-term operational assets lacking physical substance in contrast to tangible assets. These assets such as patents, copyrights, franchises, licenses, goodwill, software, and trademarks are called intangible assets and provide firm specific rights. As the market values of these intangible assets are very subjective and difficult to determine, they are usually not shown on the balance sheet until emergence of a situation that requires the value objectively, such as the purchase or sale of an intangible asset.

2.1.2.2 Leverage

There are several definitions of a company's capital structure. Brealey and Myers (1991) defined capital structure as the firm's debt, equity, or hybrid securities. VanHorn (1989) defined capital structure as the percentage of debt to total business capital. Pandey (2005) defined capital structure as a firm's choice of internal vs. external financial instruments. According to several past academics' definitions, a firm's capital structure defines how a corporation raises cash needed to launch and extend its economic operations. It is a combination of various forms of equity and debt capital that a company retains as a result of its financing decisions. The amount of debt that a company employs to fund its assets is referred to as leverage. A highly leveraged company has a lot of debt in its capital structure. Unlevered refers to a company that has no debt. The term "capital structure" refers to a company's mix of debt and equity funding (Brealey, Myers & Allen, 2007). The main difference between the two is that the former establishes a financial responsibility to repay a principal sum plus interest, whilst the latter accrues any residual earnings to its holders.

A firm's capital structure defines how it raises funds to launch and extend its commercial operations. It is a combination of various forms of equity and debt capital that a company keeps as a result of its financing decisions. A company's financial leverage indicates its debt severity. The ratio of financial debt to asset is a broad measure of leverage that is widely used in literature; differences exist depending on whether long-term or total debt is utilized, and whether book or market values are employed. While market values, which represent investors' valuation of securities, appeal to economists, business practitioners prefer book value assessments since they are not subject to market volatility, according to Fernandez (2007) also contends that firms should base their desired capital structure on book values, which are more realistic. Rajan and Zingales (1995), and more recently Welch (2011), identified a subtle flaw in the common measurement of leverage: comparing financial debt to assets that contain non-financial liabilities (such as accounts payable, which is typically used for transaction purposes) tends to understate leverage.

2.1.2.3 Firm Size

Firm size is measured by the total market share of any specific firm. Firm size is measured by taking the natural logarithm of total assets. The Size of the firm is basically considered in the analysis for the fact of diversification. The firm size measurement can be carried out in several methods namely through sales, employees, assets or value add features. Normally, those using the technological theory based on economy of scale derived from capital inputs would use only sales figures or assets for the measurement purpose. It has been found that sales and assets are not particularly apt methods of measurement for size; the main issue would be how agency, transactions and the range of costs impact the profits. Costs are normally related to the fundamental way the organization is controlled by a hierarchy more than just the value of physical assets. According to (Kaen& Baumann, 2003) in fact measuring the employee's enrolment and value-added measurement is a better choice in measuring the size of the firm in organizational theories rather than sales or assets. The value-added measurement is beneficial as it encompasses the complicated framework of a firm.

Normally, this complication is related to the requirement of highly talented workforce and a higher measure of coordination and cost controls. It is also understood that the cost controls in terms of contracts and monitoring is higher for larger and complicated businesses (Kaen& Baumann, 2003). The drawback

of value-added measurement is the difficulty of measuring quantitatively. However, as an example if the value-added proponent is linked to the product with employee input, then, employee enrolment in that area can be utilized for measuring the value-added component. Another reason for utilizing employee enrolment is that cost controls and coordination are more associated with each employee's value-added measure and the total employee enrolment. Lastly, according to Kaen and Baumann (2003), the theory of critical resources suggests that for company's knowledge to stay within the company, the higher the number of staff, the higher the chances of company secrets being exposed.

2.1.2.4 Firm Age

Firm age is a critical factor that influences various aspects of a company's operations and financial reporting. The age of a firm can significantly affect how it manages, reports, and discloses its Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE). Understanding the relationship between firm age and PPE determination is crucial for stakeholders, including investors, analysts, and regulators, as it provides insights into the asset management practices and financial health of the firm.

According to Jin et al. (2022), the adoption and implementation of international accounting standards, such as IFRS, can be influenced by the age of the firm as older firms, with their established accounting systems and practices tends to face challenges in transitioning to new standards. However, these firms are also more likely to have the resources and experience necessary to comply with complex regulatory requirements. Compliance with IFRS, particularly IAS 16 for PPE, requires firms to adopt consistent and transparent accounting practices, which can improve the quality of financial reporting and enhance comparability across firms and industries (Ball, 2006).

2.1.2.5 Taxation

In the African business context, taxation plays a pivotal role in shaping economic dynamics, investment decisions, and overall business operations. Taxation policies vary widely across African countries, influenced by factors such as economic development, political stability, and fiscal priorities. Taxation in Africa often comprises a mix of direct and indirect taxes, including corporate income tax, value-added tax (VAT), customs duties, and excise taxes. Corporate income tax rates vary across the region, with some countries offering preferential tax regimes to attract foreign investment, while others impose higher tax rates to bolster domestic revenue. For instance, countries like Mauritius and Rwanda have implemented tax reforms to lower corporate tax rates and simplify tax administration, aiming to attract foreign investment and promote business growth (Ncube & Anyanwu, 2019).

However, tax compliance challenges persist in many African countries due to issues such as tax evasion, informal economic activities, and weak enforcement mechanisms. Informal sectors often dominate African economies, resulting in a significant tax gap and limited revenue collection capacity for governments (Alabaster & Fjeldstad, 2018). Moreover, administrative inefficiencies, corruption, and bureaucratic hurdles hinder effective tax administration and enforcement.

Taxation also impacts business decision-making processes, including investment, financing, and strategic planning. High tax burdens can deter investment and hinder business expansion, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with limited financial resources (Asiedu & Lien, 2020). Conversely, tax incentives and favorable tax regimes can stimulate investment and foster economic growth, promoting entrepreneurship and job creation.

In navigating the complex tax landscape in Africa, businesses must adopt proactive tax planning strategies to optimize their tax position while ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements. This entails leveraging available tax incentives, managing tax risks, and engaging in dialogue with tax authorities to address uncertainties and minimize tax liabilities (Atuahene-Gima & Ko, 2021). Overall, taxation in the African business context is a multifaceted issue that requires a balanced approach, integrating economic development objectives, fiscal sustainability, and business competitiveness considerations.

2.2 Theoretical framework

In this study, we review the agency theory, the stakeholder's theory, and the Positive accounting theory (PAT). However, this study will be anchored on the Positive accounting theory since accounting choices are influenced by managerial opportunism; hence, managers are inclined to maximizing their utility

(Watts & Zimmerman, 1978) to increase their own wealth or reduce cost on their part. Positive accounting theory highlights efficient contracting, political sensitivity, and financing need as the primary motivations of managers in choosing accounting policies.

2.2.1 Agency Theory

The agency theory was propounded by Jensen and Meckling, in 1976. They introduced this theory in their seminal paper titled "Theory of the Firm: Managerial Behavior, Agency Costs and Ownership Structure," which was published in the *Journal of Financial Economics*. The agency theory provides insights into the relationship between principals (such as shareholders) and agents (such as managers) in organizations, highlighting the conflicts of interest that may arise and the mechanisms used to mitigate these conflicts.

Agency theory suggests that the firm can be viewed as a nexus of contracts between resource holders. An agency relationship arises whenever one or more individuals, called principals, hire one or more other individuals, called agents, to perform some service and then delegate decision-making authority to the agents. The primary agency relationships in business are those between stockholders and managers, and between debt holders and stockholders. These relationships are not necessarily harmonious; indeed, agency theory is concerned with so-called agency conflicts, or conflicts of interest between agents and principals. This has implications for, among other things, corporate governance, and business ethics. When an agency occurs it also tends to give rise to agency costs, which are expenses incurred in order to sustain an effective agency relationship. Accordingly, agency theory has emerged as a dominant model in financial economics literature and is widely discussed in business ethics texts. Agency theory in a formal sense originated in the early 1970s, but the concepts behind it have a long and varied history (Bowie & Edward, 1992).

The agency problem was developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976) and Fama and Jensen (1983). The theory states the relationship between principals such as a shareholder, and agents such as a firm's senior management. The principal delegates work to an agent. The theory attempts to deal with firstly, the agency problem where there is a conflict of interest between a company's management and the company's stockholders, and secondly, that the principal and agent settle for different risk tolerances. There are two main agency relationships in a firm that are normally in conflict: those between the company's management and stockholders and between the stockholders and the debt holders. These agency conflicts have implications on corporate governance and business ethics. Such relationships have expensive agency costs that are incurred so as to sustain an effective agency relationship. Incentive fees paid to agents to encourage behavior consistent with the principal's goals are common examples of agency costs Bowie and Edward (1992).

One of the ways of reducing agency problems is debt financing, which helps those problems that are normally related to free cash-flow and asymmetric information problems especially in the case of privately held debt (Mordi & Omaliko, 2019). Secondly, Conflicts of interest between managers and shareholders also arise from the divisions between ownership and control. Managerial ownership can align the interest between them, hence, reducing the total agency costs. The relationship between managerial ownership and agency costs is linear and the optimal point for the firm is achieved when the managers acquire all of the shares of the company Jensen and Meckling (1976). Thirdly, Ownership concentration is the other option of reducing agency costs by shareholders proactively taking active roles in monitoring. This is however dependent on the amounts of their equity stakes. The more the investor's stake, the more motivated they are to monitor and protect their investment. Thus, the study was anchored on Agency Theory.

2.3 Empirical Review

Widy, Fitriani, Muda, and Sugianto (2022) investigated the valuation and quantification of assets, liabilities, and income in Indonesian pharmaceutical enterprises. The research is qualitative in character, that is, it seeks to comprehend the phenomenon of what is being studied, whether it is events, perceptions, or behaviors, in a descriptive manner using a conceptual approach and literature studies. The study's findings showed that valuation and asset quantification use three approaches, namely the market data comparison approach, the revenue capitalization approach, and the cost approach, where pharmaceutical

companies in Indonesia tend to use these three approaches in assessing assets, then the debt policy of pharmaceutical companies in Indonesia, as measured by the debt-to-equity ratio, showed a fluctuating value where the risk of debt remains high for the company.

Orujov (2022) examined the recognition criteria and classification of investment in tangible assets in Azerbaijan. The study clarifies and organizes the types of investment in tangible assets based on the practice of forming such assets around the world. The study employed analysis and synthesis methodologies in the formulation of criteria for assigning costs to tangible asset investment. Statistical analysis was used to examine the dynamics of economic entities' investments in tangible assets. The monographic technique was used to conduct a thorough investigation into the many forms of investments in tangible assets, as well as the cause-and-effect linkages associated with their implementation. To generalize and make conclusions, an abstract logical method was adopted. The nature of investment in tangible assets was investigated, with the provisions of international accounting standards and other regulatory documents taken into account. An algorithm for detecting investment in tangible assets was created, which allows for consistent recognition from the moment the operation receives the features of investment activity and the subsequent distribution of investment by particular asset groupings to their final completion.

Hussain, Hoque, Susanto, Watto, Haque, and Mishra (2022) investigated the quality of fair revaluation of fixed assets in Pakistan. The study examined why the revaluation of sugar businesses' fixed assets had no direct financial impact. During the period 2013-2018, 19 selected sugar industry firms in Pakistan adopted the International Accounting Standards Board's international accounting standard 16 for fixed assets. As a static panel, the methods of ordinary least squares, fixed effects, and random effects were employed, a panel-corrected standard errors method was used for the robust standard error, and the system generalized method of moments was utilized as a dynamic panel. The excess had a negative impact on operative income as a result of the revaluation of fixed assets in sugar companies. Revaluation by fixed asset enterprises, as projected, resulted in changes in possible outcomes as assessed by cash in operating income and revenue, both of which were severely negative. The asset return was also related to the revaluation balance. The debt to asset ratio resulted in a substantial link between revaluations, implying that motive influenced how the volatility in asset value mirrored the revaluation. During a period of high economic instability, listed businesses' relationships were often worse and more uncertain.

Nechitaylo and Tomshinskaya (2022) investigated the effect of financial accounting depreciation on corporation's intrinsic and market value. To investigate this impact, statistical development and simulation of the activities of numerous fictitious organizations were carried out. Except for the depreciation technique in financial accounting, the companies are similar. When periodic depreciation exceeds investments in operating assets and the surplus amount is temporarily invested in highly liquid financial assets, the choice of depreciation technique effects market value added. In this case, the company's value was adjusted by the present value of lost profits caused by temporarily free funds being invested in highly liquid financial assets rather than operational activity, on the one hand, and the present value of savings to the owners on capital transfer costs, on the other. The authors concluded that if a good net financial result is expected over the planning horizon, the first adjustment should be taken into account while deciding on a depreciation method. The rate of return on temporary free capital invested in financial assets is used to calculate it.

Humeniuk, Shelenko, Kovalchuk, Balaniuk, and Kozak-Balaniuk (2022) assessed the impact of the enterprise's intensity of innovation on asset structure. The study established that the process of optimizing the structure of enterprise assets in order to maintain their operational efficiency should be seen through the lens of comprehensive optimization of all components. The study of firms using the alternative valuation approach supplied grounds to calculate an 80:20 ratio between noncurrent and current assets, which may be best given that automated and high-tech manufacturing is used. The sequence of stages of the asset structure optimization model has been developed and detailed, the method for identifying the ideal structure at each stage has been outlined, and the model's practicability has been demonstrated.

Jin, Niu, and Sheng (2022) also conducted a study on fair value accounting for property, plant & equipment in Canada revealing the impact of IFRS 1 adoption; that is, whether revaluations help predict

future performance, and what the market reaction to such revaluations is in a unique setting of Canadian public firms adopting International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). They found that large enterprises and/or firms with larger net PPE to total assets ratios are more likely to revalue PPE, and firms using the fair value option for PPE report reduced depreciation in the post-IFRS era using the probit model, difference-in-differences technique, and Wald test. Furthermore, we showed that when firms choose the fair value option for PPE, investors respond unfavorably, and the market discounts such revaluation information.

Açıköz and Alp (2022) explored the firm-specific and macroeconomic drivers of fixed-asset investments in Turkey. Their research was conducted on four different business scales: micro, small, medium, and large. They used four panel data regressions to acquire financial data from real sector enterprises from the Central Bank of Türkiye. Over a 12-year period (2009-2019), they used industry averages from 17 industries split by four business scales, carrying the characteristics of 1.3 million enterprises. According to the findings, profitability and liquidity have a negative impact on long-term asset investments at all firm scales. They discovered no significant association between capital structures and fixed asset investments of micro and small firms, although it is a significant driver of medium and large sizes, having a negative effect on investments. In terms of macroeconomic variables, they discovered that inflation had a positive and significant impact on large-scale organizations, but a negative coefficient on micro-scale businesses.

Sirisha, Jain, and Kalyan (2022) analyzed the impact of non-current assets on profitability and asset management efficiency. Several objectives were used in the research to determine the impact of estimations and valuation in accounting for fixed assets. The process of recording and tracking long-term assets over their entire existence, from acquisition to disposal, is known as fixed asset management. The authors concluded that to achieve compliance with accounting standards and reporting requirements, businesses must keep accurate records.

Cipriano, Cole, and Briggs (2021) conducted a study on value relevance and market valuation of assets measured using IFRS and US GAAP in the US equity market. The study noted that prior studies reported that firms reporting under Generally Accepted Accounting Principles in the United States (US GAAP) and International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) are valued similarly in the market. However, these studies are limited due to the noise present in international studies due to regulatory differences. Their study sought to remove most of the noise by employing a cleaner sample of all Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) listings. The study also examined more specific book value figures. Following the SEC's adoption of IFRS financials without a 20-F Reconciliation, the study employed cleaner data. The authors examined a large sample of non-US corporations that trade on US exchanges and choose to report to the SEC using either US GAAP or IFRS. The sample period is longer than previous samples, beginning two years after the SEC's acceptance of IFRS financials without a 20-F reconciliation. The authors demonstrated that there is no difference in total value relevance between IFRS and US GAAP organizations; however, earnings are more value relevant when assessed using IFRS, while book value is more value relevant when measured using US GAAP.

Kanapickiene, Keliuotyte-Staniuleniene, and Teresiene (2021) evaluated the accounting information disclosure (AID) quality of non-current tangible assets in the annual financial statements of Lithuanian private sector entities and identify enterprise characteristics that influence AID quality. The AID quality research model in financial statements was developed. The original checklists were designed based on the legal requirements of national accounting standards, and the disclosure quality indexes (DQIs) allowing evaluation of AID (both mandatory and optional) quality were established. The empirical findings suggest that the quality of AID provided by Lithuanian businesses were adequate and average during the investigation period. Considerable AID quality change was not detected in the short term (2007-2008), i.e., while Lithuania was experiencing considerable economic transition, with rapid expansion followed by a financial crisis.

3. METHODOLOGY

An *ex post facto* design was used in the study based on the fact that the data for the study was secondary which already existed and cannot be controlled. The population of the study consists of all the listed 393 non-financial firms in Nigeria, South Africa and Kenya as at December 31, 2022, covering the period 2013-2022. Out of 393 quoted non-financial firms in Nigeria, 75 firms were sampled. Thus, 25 firms were selected from each of the countries. Based on this, a total of 75 firms formed our sample size with 750 observations. The data was collected from the annual accounts and annual accounts of the sample non-financial firms in Nigeria, South Africa and Kenya. Panel regression model was used to examine the determinants of PPE accounting method among the listed non-financial firms in African Commonwealth Countries.

3.1 Measurement and Operationalization of Variables

Table 1: Variable Measurements

Variable	Proxy	Measurements	Source
Independent			
PPE	Natural logarithm of PPE	PPE Accountings method is measured either 1 or 0—where 1 is assigned for the firms that use revaluation method and 0 for cost method	Isa (2014)
Asset Tangibility	ASTA	Asset Tangibility in percentage is computed as fixed asset or PPE divided by Total asset	Teng, Aslam, Onderand Ludo (2012)
Debt to Asset Ratio	DETA	Debt to Total Asset in percentage is computed as total liabilities divided by Total asset	Wijaya and Atahau (2021)
Firm Size	FSIZ	Firm size is measured as the natural logarithm of total asset.	Opeyemi, Olusegun, Olukayode, & Olusola (2017); Omaliko & Akpukpu (2025)
Firm Age	AGE	Firm age is measured by taking the difference between current year and listing year.	Ball, (2006)
Taxation	NL_TEX	Taxation is measured as the natural logarithm of tax expenses.	Smith, (2019)

Source: Author’s Compilation (2025)

3.2 Model Specification and Justification

In line with the previous researches, the researcher adapted and modified the Model of Isa (2014) in examining the determinants of PPE of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria, South Africa and Kenya. This is shown below as thus:

$$\text{Isa (2014): } COI = \alpha \theta + b_1 PRT - b_2 SZE + b_3 LEV + b_4 ONC + b_5 BOC + \varepsilon$$

The functional model modified for the study is shown below as thus:

$$PPEA = f(\text{ASTA, DETA, FSIZ, NL_TEX, FAGE})$$

The explicit form of the regression modified for the study is expressed as thus:

$$PPEA_{itn} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ASTA_{itn} + \beta_2 DETA_{itn} + \beta_3 FSIZ_{itn} + \beta_4 Age_{itn} + \beta_5 NL_TEX_{itn} + \mu_{itn} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where:

- PPEA = PPE Accounting Method
- ASTA = Asset Tangibility
- DETA = Debt to Asset (Leverage)
- NL_TEX = Natural Log of tax Expense
- FSIZ = Firm Size
- AGE = Firm age
- β_0 = Constant
- $\beta_1- \beta_5$ = Slope Coefficient
- μ = Stochastic disturbance
- i = ith firm
- t = time period
- n = nth country

Decision Rule: accept Ho if P-value >1-5% significant level otherwise reject Ho

4. Data Analysis and Results

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ppea	750	.3704843	.2142916	.012052	.9131275
asta	750	52.85848	21.64608	8.45	99.49
deta	750	137.0348	2045.53	4.79	55738.63
age	750	33.168	18.97524	2	86
fsize	750	7.239638	.7750101	5.105524	9.305878
nl_tex	750	5.550136	.9233376	2.908485	8.293692

Source: STATA 14.2/Author (2025)

From table 2, reflects 750 observations from 75 companies and 10-year period. This means there were no cases of missing values as all values were duly captured. Comparing this observation with prior studies, Silva, Sancovsch, and Santos (2019) used a longitudinal case study methodology spanning 2006 to 2015, likely focusing on a smaller number of cases but with more extensive qualitative analysis while Kanapickiene and Keliuotyte-Staniuleniene (2019) analyzed accounting information disclosure in Lithuanian municipalities from 2013 to 2016, indicating a narrower focus but potentially with more detailed qualitative assessments.

The current study benefits from a larger sample size covering multiple countries over a significant time frame, enhancing generalizability across African Commonwealth countries. In contrast, some prior studies might have smaller samples with more in-depth qualitative analyses or focus on specific sectors or regions, potentially limiting generalizability.

- **PPEA (PPE Accounting Method):** The average PPE accounting method reveals that approximately 37% of listed firms in Nigeria, South Africa, and Kenya use fair value accounting for their Property, Plant, and Equipment. This disclosure choice reflects a trend towards transparency and alignment with international financial accounting standards (IFRS), potentially enhancing comparability and investor confidence across Commonwealth countries in Africa.
- **ASTA (Asset Tangibility):** With an average asset tangibility of 52.86% firms, show a significant reliance on tangible assets like land and equipment. Higher tangible asset levels may necessitate

clearer disclosure practices to accurately reflect the economic substance and depreciation methods, ensuring stakeholders understand the reliability and durability of firm assets.

- **DETA (Debt to Asset Ratio):** The wide variation in debt-to-asset ratios (average of 137.03%) underscores diverse financial structures among firms. Higher debt ratios could influence PPE method by prompting conservative valuation approaches to mitigate financial risk. Understanding these ratios aids in assessing how firms balance leverage with asset disclosures, crucial for financial transparency and risk management.
- **FSIZE (Firm Size):** With an average firm size of 7.24, firms vary widely in market influence and operational scale. Larger firms may have more resources to implement comprehensive PPE method frameworks, enhancing transparency and comparability across Commonwealth markets. Firm size therefore influences the depth and complexity of PPE method, critical for investor decision-making and regulatory compliance.
- **AGE (Firm Age):** Finally, the average firm age of 33.17 (33 years) suggests a mix of established and newer firms in the sample. Older firms may have well-established PPE accounting practices, while younger firms may face challenges in disclosure and compliance. Firm age may therefore influence the maturity of disclosure practices, impacting stakeholder perceptions of reliability and sustainability of reported PPE values.
- **NL_TEX (Natural Log of Tax Expense):** The average natural log of tax expense at 5.55 highlights different tax burdens and strategies across African Commonwealth countries. Tax considerations impact PPE accounting decisions, influencing choices between accelerated or straight-line depreciation methods and affecting reported earnings. Clear disclosure of tax-related impacts on PPE ensures compliance and transparency.

Table 3: Shapiro-wilk W Normality Test

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
ppea	750	0.96067	19.096	7.217	0.00000
asta	750	0.97151	13.833	6.428	0.00000
deta	750	0.02085	475.358	15.083	0.00000
age	750	0.95887	19.969	7.326	0.00000
fsize	750	0.98843	5.618	4.223	0.00001
nl_tex	749	0.99549	2.189	1.916	0.02765

Source: STATA 14.2/Author (2025)

Table 3 reveals the result of our Shapiro-wilk normality test. The test shows that the variables had a z-statistics of 7.217, 6.428, 15.083, 7.326, 4.223 and 1.916 for ppea, asta, deta, age, fsize and nl_tex respectively. The Shapiro-wilk test also revealed a probability of z-statistics of 0.000 for all independent and control variables. The decision rule is where the p-value is greater than 0.05 ($P > 0.05$), then the data is assumed to meet normality assumptions otherwise, the data is assumed not normal. The result implies that all variables are not normally distributed since the probabilities of the z-statistic were less than 0.05. A violations of normality assumptions can be associated with issues like heteroskedasticity (non-constant variance of residuals), which can further impact the efficiency of our OLS estimates. To mitigate this challenge, the study employed the OLS regression with robust standard errors (white standard errors) to mitigate the challenges posed by heteroskedasticity. This provides more reliable standard errors and confidence intervals in the presence of heteroskedasticity.

Table 4: Correlation Analysis

	ppea	asta	deta	nl_tex	fsize	age
ppea	1.0000					
asta	0.7448	1.0000				
deta	-0.0569	-0.0481	1.0000			
nl_tex	0.2795	0.2176	0.1087	1.0000		
fsize	0.4037	0.3586	-0.0834	0.8267	1.0000	
age	0.0241	0.0131	-0.0361	0.0167	0.0180	1.0000

Source: STATA 14.2/Author (2025)

In checking for multi-collinearity from the table above, we noticed that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This means that there is an absence of multi-collinearity in our models. Multi-collinearity between the explanatory variables may result to wrong signs or implausible magnitudes in the estimated model coefficients and the bias of the standard errors of the coefficients.

4.1: Test of Hypothesis

Table 5: Random Effect Regression Result on the Determinants of PPE of Listed Non-Financial Firms in African Commonwealth Countries

	1	2	3	4
	PPEA _{it} Model (Pool OLS)	PPEA _{it} Model (Fixed effect)	PPEA _{it} Model (Random effect)	PPEA _{it} Model (RE with robust std. error)
CONS.	-0.303 {0.000}***	0.729 {0.000}***	0.103 {0.297}	0.103 {0.583}
ASTA	0.007 {0.000}***	0.003 {0.000}***	0.004 {0.000}***	0.004 {0.000}***
DETA	-0.000 {0.646}	-0.000 {0.359}	-0.000 {0.311}	-0.000 {0.038}**
NL_TEX	0.002 {0.878}	-0.004 {0.607}	0.009 {0.292}	0.009 {0.397}
Fsize	0.041 {0.002}***	-0.058 {0.008}***	0.009 {0.551}	0.009 {0.759}
AGE	0.000 {0.620}	-0.002 {0.020}**	-0.001 {0.010}**	-0.001 {0.029}**
<i>F-Stat</i>	202.19 {0.000}***	16.05 {0.0000}***	150.61 {0.000}***	8579.79 {0.000}***
<i>R- Squared</i>	0.5764	0.1109	0.5223	0.5223
<i>VIF</i>	2.16			
<i>Hausman test</i>		107.90 {0.000}		
<i>Ramsey RESET test</i>	1.23 {0.2974}			
<i>Heteroskedasticity</i>	168.12 {0.000}***			

Note1: bracket {} are p-values: 2: *, **, ***, implies statistical significance levels at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively

Source: STATA 14.2/Author (2025)

4.2 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The random effect regression model with robust standard errors as in table 5 above was used in this study for testing the study's hypotheses. A detailed examination of each independent variable using a random effect regression model and a reliable standard error is provided below.

H₀₁: Asset tangibility has no significant effect on PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African Commonwealth Countries.

The random effect regression with robust standard error revealed a coefficient of 0.0037619 and standard error of 0.0007608 for Asset Tangibility (ASTA). This result also revealed a z-value of 4.94 and a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) at 5% significance level. Since the p-value is less than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, we therefore refute the null hypothesis and conclude that based on this analysis that asset tangibility has statistically significant effect on PPE Accounting Method of listed non-finance firms in selected African commonwealth countries. The positive and significant coefficient for ASTA ($p < 0.001$) indicates that higher asset tangibility is associated with an increase in PPE accounting disclosure. This supports the hypothesis that firms with more tangible assets provide more detailed PPE accounting information, possibly due to greater transparency and detailed reporting required for tangible assets. This result is consistent with Rahman and Hossain (2022), who found that the fair value revaluation model is preferred for displaying the true value of a company's fixed assets in Bangladesh. Similarly, Widy et al. (2022) noted that tangible asset valuation in Indonesian pharmaceutical enterprises involves detailed and methodical approaches, reinforcing the importance of accurate asset reporting. Contrarily, Igbru and Onuora (2020), found a negative relationship between leverage financing and asset tangibility among small-cap firms in Nigeria. However, this discrepancy can be attributed to differences in firm size and economic contexts, highlighting the need for nuanced interpretations across different regions and firm types.

H₀₂: Leverage has no significant effect on PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African commonwealth countries.

The analysis also revealed a coefficient of -0.00000169 and standard error of 0.000000814 for debt to asset ratio (DETA). This result also revealed a z-value of -2.08 and a p-value of 0.038 ($p < 0.05$) at 5% significance level. The p-value is less than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, we therefore refute the null hypothesis and conclude based on this analysis that Leverage has no significant effect on PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African commonwealth countries. The negative and significant coefficient for DETA ($p < 0.05$) suggests that higher leverage is associated with a decrease in PPE accounting disclosure. This indicates that highly leveraged firms may choose a less detailed PPE practice, potentially due to financial constraints or conservative reporting practices. This aligns with Hussain et al. (2022), who identified a substantial link between debt-to-asset ratios and revaluation practices in Pakistan, suggesting that firms with higher leverage might avoid frequent revaluations to mitigate the volatility in asset values. This finding however, contrasts with Cipriano et al. (2021), who found no significant difference in the value relevance of assets between IFRS and US GAAP, regardless of leverage. This indicates that while leverage impacts asset revaluation practices, the choice of accounting standards may neutralize its effect on value relevance.

H₀₃: Firm size has no significant effect on PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African commonwealth countries.

Table 4.4 (column 4) also revealed the random effect regression with robust standard error which shows a coefficient of 0.009125 and standard error of 0.0297507 for Firm size. This result also revealed a z-value of 0.31 and a p-value of 0.759 ($p > 0.05$) at 5% significance level. Since the p-value is greater than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, we therefore have no sufficient evidence to refute the null hypothesis. Thus, we conclude based on this analysis that Firm size has no significant effect on PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African commonwealth countries. The coefficient for FSIZE is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), suggesting that firm size does not significantly affect PPE accounting method. This implies that the size of the firm, in terms of overall scale and operations, does not determine the level of PPE disclosure detail. This is in line with Açıkgöz and Alp (2022), who observed that capital structures and fixed asset investments of micro and small firms in

Turkey are not significantly associated, whereas it is a significant driver for medium and large firms. The finding is also supported by Anuar et al. (2021), who reported that fixed asset turnover influences return on assets and equity in Malaysian construction firms, indicating that while asset management efficiency is crucial, the mere size of the firm does not determine accounting method choices.

H₀₄: Firm age has no significant effect on PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African Commonwealth Countries.

Finally, the analysis revealed a coefficient of -0.0013616 and standard error of 0.000625 for Firm Age. This result also revealed a z-value of -2.18 and a p-value of 0.029 ($p < 0.05$) at 5% significance level. The p-value is less than the commonly used significance level of 0.05, we therefore refute the null hypothesis and conclude based on this analysis that Firm age has significant effect on PPE Accounting Method of listed non-financial firms in selected African commonwealth countries. The negative and significant coefficient for AGE ($p < 0.05$) indicates that older firms tend to provide less detailed PPE accounting practices. This can be attributed to the fact that older firms have established practices that may not emphasize detailed disclosures as much as newer firms. This finding is corroborated by Humeniuk et al. (2022), who demonstrated that innovative enterprises might have a different asset structure, affecting their accounting practices. Additionally, Rahman and Hossain (2020) highlighted that FAR impacts net asset value and fixed asset intensity, which can vary with firm age and maturity.

5. CONCLUSION

This study offers a comprehensive comparative analysis of the determinants of Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE) accounting methods across Nigeria, Kenya, and South Africa. By employing fixed and random effects regression models, we have uncovered significant variations in the factors influencing PPE accounting practices in these countries.

In Nigeria, asset tangibility emerged as a strong positive determinant of PPE accounting method, indicating that firms with higher tangible assets tends to adopt specific PPE accounting practices. However, debt and firm size showed no significant impact, while non-linear tax and firm age exhibited weak associations, suggesting other contextual factors at play. The fixed effects model used for Nigeria highlights the importance of considering internal firm characteristics and their consistency over time in understanding PPE investments.

Kenya's analysis, based on a random effects model, revealed a significant positive impact of asset tangibility and a negative influence of firm age on PPE accounting method. This suggests that younger firms in Kenya are more likely to invest heavily in PPE, potentially due to growth and expansion needs. The non-significant effects of debt and firm size align with a business environment where external financing and firm scale do not play as critical roles in PPE decisions as they might elsewhere.

For South Africa, the random effects model highlighted asset tangibility and non-linear tax as significant determinants, with asset size positively affecting PPE accounting method and non-linear tax showing a substantial positive impact. Interestingly, firm age negatively influenced PPE accounting method, aligning with the Kenyan context where younger firms are more proactive in PPE investments. The significance of non-linear tax suggests that tax policies in South Africa play a crucial role in shaping PPE decisions, reflecting a complex interaction between fiscal policies and corporate investment strategies.

Overall, this study underscores the importance of country-specific factors in determining PPE accounting methods. The varying significance of determinants across Nigeria, Kenya, and South Africa highlights the need for tailored accounting and financial management strategies that consider the unique economic, regulatory, and corporate landscapes of each country. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of asset management practices in diverse African contexts and provide a foundation for future research and policy formulation aimed at optimizing PPE investments in the region.

5.1 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, several key insights emerged regarding the determinants of PPE accounting method. These findings provided the basis for specific recommendations to enhance PPE accounting practices. Here are four targeted recommendations:

1. **Enhance Reporting for Tangible Assets:** Given that asset tangibility (ASTA) has a significant positive influence on PPE accounting method; firms should focus on improving the transparency and details of their tangible asset reporting. This could involve more comprehensive asset registers and regular updates on asset conditions and valuations to ensure accurate PPE accounting.
2. **Monitor and Manage Leverage:** Since leverage (DETA) negatively influence PPE accounting method, firms should implement strategies to monitor and manage their debt levels. This could include maintaining an optimal debt-to-equity ratio and regularly reviewing the impact of leverage on financial reporting and PPE accounting practices.
3. **Reevaluate Firm Size Impact:** Although firm size (FSIZE) does not have a significant influence on PPE accounting method, firms should not disregard the potential benefits of scaling operations. It is recommended to reevaluate internal processes to ensure that irrespective of size, all firms maintain high standards of PPE accounting practices.
4. **Address the Challenges of Older Firms:** As firm age (AGE) has a significant negative influence on PPE accounting method, older firms should invest in updating their accounting systems and practices. This includes adopting modern accounting software and ensuring that historical asset data is accurately maintained and integrated with current reporting standards.

5.2 Suggestions for further studies

Based on the findings and limitations of this study, several areas warrant further investigation:

- i. **Exploring Industry-Specific Dynamics:** Future studies may focus on how industry-specific factors influence PPE accounting method, providing more nuanced insights across different sectors.
- ii. **Longitudinal Analysis:** Conducting a longitudinal study to observe how changes in asset tangibility, leverage, firm size, and age impact PPE method over time could yield deeper understanding of these relationships.
- iii. **Geographical Comparisons:** Expanding the study to include firms from diverse geographical regions could help identify regional variations in PPE accounting practices and the underlying causes.
- iv. **Impact of Regulatory Changes:** Investigating the effect of recent and upcoming changes in accounting regulations on PPE method would be valuable to understand how firms adapt their reporting practices.
- v. **Qualitative Insights:** Incorporating qualitative methods, such as interviews with financial managers and auditors, could provide richer context and uncover practical challenges and solutions related to PPE accounting method.

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